

HYPERVELOCITY IMPACT DAMAGE TO COMPOSITE MATERIALS

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SUMMARY: This paper describes an experimental program undertaken to study the impact damage of laminated graphite/PEEK plates and cylinders subjected to particle impacts at velocities ranging from 3 to 7 km/s. This velocity range corresponds to that found in space due to impacting micrometeoroids and space debris (MOD). To assess this problem, impact tests were conducted at three facilities in the U.S., with most of the tests undertaken at the NASA Johnson Space Center in Houston, using their two-stage light gas guns. Aluminum spheres were fired at composite material targets using various diameters and velocities to determine the damage correlation with energy, laminate thickness and material properties. Flat plate targets were first investigated to establish damage thresholds, followed by tests on laminated cylinders characteristic of the robot arm structures being designed for the Space Station. This paper presents the results of these studies showing the correlations found in terms of impact crater size, front face total damage, rear face spallation damage and secondary damage resulting from the ejecta plume impacting the rear wall of the cylinder.

KEYWORDS: hypervelocity impact damage, composite materials, orbital debris, design.

INTRODUCTION

Spacecraft in low Earth orbit (LEO) are vulnerable to impact damage resulting from collisions with micrometeoroids and orbital debris (MOD). Micrometeoroids originate naturally from planetary or asteroidal collisions and cometary ejecta. Although there is no particular direction in which micrometeoroids approach the Earth, spacecraft experience a bias in the direction of travel (known as the RAM direction). This can readily be seen from the impact distributions measured on the NASA Long Duration Exposure Facility (LDEF) which spent almost six years in space. Figure 1 presents this data for impacts arising from the MOD environment and it is quite apparent that the RAM direction recorded significantly more impacts, although it is noteworthy that even the back surface was hit as well. Artificial space debris consists of everything from spent satellites and rockets to aluminum oxide fuel particles, paint chips and fragmentation objects from collisions of these bodies in orbit. A plot of the MOD environment as a function of altitude and particle size is shown in Fig. 2. Although micrometeoroids have been a design issue since the 1960's, concern about the growing amount of orbital debris did not receive serious attention until the mid-1980's. The problem has grown to such an extent that the probability of impact by space debris exceeds that due to micrometeoroids in some cases. There is currently an astounding 2.5×10^6 kg of debris in LEO. Since first entering space in 1957, almost 20,000 objects have been launched with approximately 7,000 still in orbit.

Polymer matrix composites are used extensively in spacecraft structures and components, such as antenna struts, panels and low distortion frames. The largest composite structure in space is the Canadian robot arm on all of the Space Shuttles. A much more complex robot system consisting of graphite/PEEK tubes is currently being assembled for the Space Station Remote Manipulator System. Although these materials provide significant advantages in terms of high specific stiffness and strength, as well as low thermal expansion properties, the problem of MOD impact damage needs to be addressed.

Fig. 1: Circumferential distribution of micrometeoroid/debris impacts on LDEF (NASA M&D/SIG Rept; Aug. 1990).

Fig. 2: Micrometeoroid and orbital debris flux vs. particle size as a function of altitude (NASA CR#BB000883A, Jan. 1991).

Very few studies have been conducted on MOD hypervelocity impact (HVI) damage to polymer matrix composites. Some of the earlier work on graphite/epoxy plates includes that done by Yew et al [1] (identified in graphs as “Austin” data) at the NASA Johnson Space Center in 1986 using two of their light gas guns to achieve hypervelocity impact conditions. A wide range of plate thicknesses was investigated using quasi-isotropic lay-ups.

A more detailed series of tests was reported by Christiansen in 1988 [2] (identified in graphs as “Eagle” data) in which both low and high modulus graphite/epoxy plates and tubes were studied. Again, various target thicknesses were used and different impact angles were employed. It was observed that fiber modulus has a greater effect than lay-up. Christiansen developed two impact damage models based on this data for energies above and below 150 J. Lower energy impact data on both graphite/epoxy and PEEK plates were reported in [3] (identified as “Auburn” data) but the range of test parameters was very restricted.

The following report presents the results of a series of tests on PEEK/IM7 and PEEK/AS-4 flat plate and cylinder laminates of varying thickness and lay-ups conducted at the NASA Johnson Space Center (JSC” data), the Southwest Research Institute (“SwRI” data), and the NASA Marshall Space Flight Center (“MSFC” data) using their two-stage light gas guns.

EXPERIMENTS

Test Set-Up

A series of flat plates (primary target) were tested in these facilities with a second plate (secondary target) located about 33 cm behind the primary impact plate. The purpose of the second plate was to determine the ejecta damage emanating from the first wall impact and assess the extent of rear wall penetration and overall structural degradation (i.e., loss in stiffness and strength). All tests were conducted with aluminum impactor spheres of varying diameter and at different velocities. Energies ranging from 2 to 2000 J were investigated. In the following graphs, results from other test programs are also included for comparison purposes. A summary of our test data is presented below in Table 1.

Table 1: HVI shot matrix performed on graphite/PEEK composite

Shot Id	Configuration	Primary Target		Secondary Target		Projectile		
		Thickness [mm]	Layup	Thickness [mm]	Layup	Diameter [mm]	Velocity [m/s]	Energy [J]
JSC #1	PEEK & Al proj. (0 deg.)	2.7	(+/-43)s	0.5	(0,90)s	1.5	6.05	90.6
JSC #2	PEEK & Al proj. (0 deg.)	2.0	(0,+/-45,90)s	1.9	(0,+/-45,90)s	2	6.75	267.2
JSC #3	PEEK & Al proj. (0 deg.)	1.8	(0,+/-45,90)s	2.0	(0,+/-45,90)s	3	6	712.5
JSC #4	PEEK & Al proj. (0 deg.)	0.5	(0,90)s	0.5	(0,90)s	1.5	7	121.2
JSC #5	PEEK & Al proj. (0 deg.)	2.9	(0,+/-45,90)s	2.9	(0,+/-45,90)s	2.5	6.98	558.0
JSC #6	PEEK & Al proj. (0 deg.)	2.7	(+/-43)s	2.0	(0,+/-45,90)s	2	7.2	304.0
JSC #7	PEEK & Al proj. (0 deg.)	2.7	(+/-43)s	1.9	(0,+/-45,90)s	2.5	6.85	537.4
JSC #8	PEEK & Al proj. (0 deg.)	2.9	(0,+/-45,90)s	1.9	(0,+/-45,90)s	2.5	6.21	441.7
JSC #9	PEEK & Al proj. (0 deg.)	1.0	(0,+/-45,90)s	0.9	(0,+/-45,90)s	2	5	146.6
SwRI #1	PEEK & Al proj. (0 deg.)	0.5	(0,90)s	0.5	(0,90)s	1	6.82	20.9
SwRI #2	PEEK & Al proj. (0 deg.)	0.9	(0,+/-45,90)s	1.0	(0,+/-45,90)s	1	7.27	23.8
SwRI #3	PEEK & Al proj. (0 deg.)	2.9	(0,+/-45,90)s	2.9	(0,+/-45,90)s	1	7.18	23.2
SwRI #4	PEEK & Al proj. (0 deg.)	0.4	(0,90)s	0.5	(0,90)s	0.4	6.26	2.0
SwRI #5	PEEK & Al proj. (0 deg.)	1.9	(0,+/-45,90)s	1.9	(0,+/-45,90)s	1	7.18	25.8
SwRI #6	PEEK & Al proj. (0 deg.)	1.9	(0,+/-45,90)s	1.9	(0,+/-45,90)s	0.4	7.3	2.7
SwRI #7	PEEK & Al proj. (0 deg.)	1.0	(0,+/-45,90)s	1.0	(0,+/-45,90)s	0.4	7.07	2.5
MSFC #1	PEEK & Al proj. (0 deg.)	0.9	(0,+/-45,90)s	0.9	(0,+/-45,90)s	4.0	6.57	1978

A subsequent series of tests on composite cylinders were performed using the 0.50 Cal two-stage light gas gun at the Johnson Space Center. The gun is equipped with a Cordin high-speed camera system, capable of snapping 2.25 million frames per second of the projectile impact and the debris cloud formation processes. The cylinder targets were 30 cm long, 33 cm in diameter and 2.7 mm thick. Aluminum spherical projectiles, 3.18 mm to 9.13 mm in diameter, travelling at velocities ranging from 6.4 km/s to 6.91 km/s, were used in all of the experiments. Only normal impacts were performed. The test results for this series are summarized below in Table 2.

Table 2: HVI database for the composite cylinder targets.

Target Shot Id	Projectile			Damage
	D_p [mm]	V [km/s]	E [J]	D_c^* [mm]
#1	3.18	6.4	961	8.5
#2	5.16	6.8	4646	13.2
#3	5.95	6.91	7396	14.3
#4	9.13	6.56	24007	18.3
#5	9.13	6.56	24009	18.4
#6	9.13	6.55	23937	18.2

*The equivalent circular diameter (D_c) represents the diameter of a circle which encompasses the same area as the irregularly-shaped crater hole or damage area.

HYPERVELOCITY IMPACT (HVI) TEST RESULTS

Entry Crater Damage

The entry crater model derived from the HVI data is presented in Fig. 3. It is based on a functional relationship between the observed entry crater diameter, D_c^* (mm), and an energy

parameter $\sqrt[3]{E \frac{t}{D_p}}$, where E is the projectile's kinetic energy (Joules), t is the target thickness (mm), and D_p is the projectile diameter (mm). This parameter was first introduced by Christiansen [2] for use with composites, and is reused in this report with similar success.

Although other test data for graphite/epoxy materials are included, the model is fitted with a regression line, forced to pass through zero, which only considers those data points involving PEEK matrix targets, impacted with aluminum or glass spherical projectiles.

Each entry in the legend of the graph provides four distinct pieces of information. A legend entry consists of a data point marker, the test series alias, the type of target material (carbon fibre/PEEK or GRE), and the type of projectile material (aluminum, glass, or nylon). For example, a legend entry such as : "■ JSC PEEK (Al)" implies that solid squares on the graph represent data points for the "JSC" test series using PEEK based composite targets. The projectiles used in the experiments are aluminium spheres.

Fig. 3: Entry crater model.

The functional relationship is given by,

$$D_c = .93 \sqrt[3]{E \frac{t}{D_p}} \quad (1)$$

The model is generally applicable to PEEK and epoxy matrix based composites. The carbon fibres used all have a modulus in between 135 and 235 GPa. Applicable laminate thicknesses range from 0.5 mm up to 6.7 mm. The model is independent of laminate lay-up. It is consistent for a broad range of projectile diameters, extending from 0.4 mm to 9.13 mm, travelling at velocities ranging from 4 to 7.5 km/s. Aluminum, glass, and nylon projectiles are compatible with the model.

Total Entry Damage

From a design point of view, the entry damage on the front face is more critical since it includes the crater hole and associated damage to the laminate. Entry damage, as defined by the equivalent diameter method, is plotted in Fig. 4 as a function of the same energy parameter. Included in this plot is the regression curve based on C-scan measurements of the sub-surface damage zones. It can be seen that even though the delamination lies below the surface, the enhanced area is only about 20% greater than the surface area. The entry damage area can be estimated from measuring the crater area, based on the equivalent diameter method, using the formula: $Entry\ Area = 20 \times Crater\ Area$.

Fig. 4: Entry damage diameter vs. $\sqrt[3]{E \frac{t}{D_p}}$.

Rear face spallation damage on the primary impact plate was also measured, the results of which are plotted in Fig. 5. The regression analysis indicates that the damage area is comparable to that observed on the front face for a given energy parameter.

Fig. 5: Spall damage diameter vs. $\sqrt[3]{E \frac{t}{D_p}}$.

Fig. 6: Crater vs. projectile diameter.

A plot of the crater diameter as a function of the projectile diameter is shown in Fig. 6. The regression curve was constructed only through the PEEK data, excluding the nylon cylinder results. There appears to be no energy dependence for the range of parameters studied. Interestingly, one can see that the nylon results correlate with the curve quite well, although the sub-millimeter SiC particle impact data do not agree at all. Generally, one can assume that for hypervelocity impacts for particles greater than 1 mm in diameter, the crater hole size produced will be about 2.7 x the projectile diameter. Below this threshold, it would appear that the hole diameter can be taken as equal to the particle diameter.

SECONDARY DEBRIS PLUME DAMAGE

Considerable effort was made to investigate the debris plume size and corresponding damage to the rear plate. The debris plume is composed of impactor fracture particles and delaminated spallation particles. Based on detailed mapping of the debris impact sites (see Fig. 7), the primary debris plume cone angle was measured for flat plates. These results are plotted in Fig. 8 and demonstrate a consistent angle of about 11.6°.

The next series of experiments using the composite cylinders produced some valuable insight into the debris and ejecta cloud processes. The Cordin high-speed camera is capable of snapping approximately 80 frames of the target over the entire impact process, for an elapsed time of about 100 μ s.

They depict the progression of the intact projectile, the initial impact, the formation of the debris cloud, and finally, the rejection of ejecta out the front surface of the cylinder. An excerpt of the footage produced in the #4 experiment is shown in Fig. 9. In the first frame, the incoming projectile can be seen just prior to impacting the surface of the cylinder. In the subsequent frames, the formation of the secondary debris and ejecta clouds is clearly apparent. Analysis of the debris cloud velocity reveals that the cloud tip travels at approximately the same velocity as the projectile.

Fig. 7: 87 distinct craters catalogued.

Fig. 8: Debris cone angle vs. $\sqrt[3]{E \frac{t}{D_p}}$.

The energetic debris clouds generated in shots #4 and #6 completely destroyed the rear wall of the cylinder, as can be seen in Fig. 10. The photographic analysis, combined with post impact visual observations of the cylinders, yields a debris cloud cone angle of,

$$\theta_{dc} \approx 17^\circ \tag{2}$$

where θ_{dc} represents the 100 mm cutout radius of holes from the debris cloud. For the cylinders tested, the damage zone was about 200 mm in diameter. This is more than the 11.6°

previously found during the flat plate tests. The vastly higher impact energies involved may contribute to the wider debris cloud spread.

Fig. 9: High-speed photography of the impact process in model #4.

Fig. 10

STRUCTURAL FAILURE ASSESSMENT

In the design of a composite structure for spacecraft applications, there are two apparent failure modes which must be considered:

1. An energetic MOD fragment creates a large crater and surrounding damage area, causing structural failure.
2. An energetic secondary debris cloud destroys a larger area of the rear wall of an enclosed composite structure (such as a cylinder).

The first scenario, structural failure of the cylinders due to a large entry crater, is highly unlikely, due to the improbability of encountering a large enough MOD particle. However, the fracture damage from the debris plume is sufficiently large in area to cause a major reduction in structural stiffness and buckling strength. For example, the effect of a 200 mm diameter 'cutout' on the buckling strength of a cylinder is shown in Fig. 11. Strength reductions of the order of 52% and 61% were found for compression (F_x), torsion (M_x) and bending (M_y) loading, respectively.

Fig. 11: Effect of cutouts on reduction of buckling strengths.

CONCLUSIONS

As part of this study, two dozen HVI experiments were conducted using flat plate and cylindrical sections of PEEK matrix based composites. Many parallel studies were uncovered which had investigated HVI response in similar composites. All of these experiments were amalgamated to form an extensive HVI database specific to carbon fibre PEEK and epoxy based composites.

From the database, an entry crater damage model was produced. The entry crater diameter was found to be functionally dependent on a defined energy parameter, $\sqrt[3]{E \frac{t}{D_p}}$, over a wide range of target thickness, lay-up, fibre and matrix material, as well as projectile diameter,

velocity, energy, geometry, and composition. In general, the crater diameter can be modelled by the relationship $D_c = .93 \sqrt[3]{E \frac{t}{D_p}}$.

The initial projectile impact produces a secondary debris cloud of high energy projectile and target fragments. The debris cloud cone angle, which spans the radius of influence attributable to debris cloud damage, was estimated to be 17°, as observed during tests on the cylinders. The secondary debris cloud is capable of producing severe damage to any spacecraft composite component lying in its path.

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